

Spectrophotometric method for the determination of metaformin hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulations and human urine samples

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Abstract : The main aim of the present work is spectrophotometric method for the assaying of oral anti-hyperglycemic agent metaformin. The method is based on the oxidation of metaformin with 2,2'-bipyridyl followed by Fe^{III} in presence of orthophosphoric acid to exhibit orange red chromogen at 550 nm. The drug follows linearity in the concentration range 2-20 µg/ml with a correlation coefficient value of 0.998. The developed method was successfully applied for the assay of metaformin in bulk, pharmaceutical formulations and human urine samples. Statistical analysis proves that the method is simple, rapid, sensitive and reproducible. The results obtained by the developed method are in good agreement with the labelled amounts.

Keywords : Metaformin, 2,2'-bipyridyl, formulations, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Metaformin hydrochloride chemically 1,1-dimethyl biguanide hydrochloride¹ is an oral anti-hyperglycemic agent and is used in the treatment of non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of metaformin hydrochloride.

In literature some methods like HPLC²⁻⁵ and spectrophotometric⁶⁻⁸ have been reported for the estimation of the metaformin hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulations and biological samples.

However no spectrophotometric method using 2,2'-bipyridyl as reagent was reported for estimation of metaformin hydrochloride in formulations and human urine sample. The present work describes a new simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method to determine metaformin concentration in formulations and human urine sample.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Absorbance measurements were made using Shimadzu-2450 UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched quartz cells.

Reagents :

All the chemicals (SD Fine Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai) used were of analytical reagent grade; double distilled water was used for the preparation of reagents and samples. Metaformin hydrochloride bulk drug was obtained as gift sample from Micro Labs, Bangalore, India. Pharmaceutical formulations of metaformin were obtained commercially.

Standard drug solution :

Twenty tablets of metaformin are weighed and powdered. The tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg was placed into a 100 ml volumetric flask containing 50 ml of water. It is kept at ultrasonication for 5 min, then it is diluted up to the mark with methanol and the solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41 to get concentration 1 mg/ml. From the above solution 10 ml is pipetted out into 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume is made up to the mark with methanol. The final concentration of

metaformin is brought to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and used for the analysis.

Procedure :

Aliquots of metaformin ranging from 2–20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each flask, 1 ml of aqueous solution of ferric chloride (0.5% w/v) and 1.0 ml methanolic solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl (0.2% w/v) were added, heated on a water bath for 15 min cooled to room temperature and then added 1 ml of orthophosphoric acid. The final volume was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the orange red coloured species formed was measured at 550 nm against reagent blank and Beer's law was obeyed in concentration range of 2–20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The absorbance of reaction product at 550 nm remained stable for more than 3 h. The amount of metaformin present in the sample was computed from calibration curve (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Calibration plot for the developed method.

Results and discussion

The 2,2'-bipyridyl is an organic base and contains iron(II) specific group. Proposed method is based on the formation of tris(2,2'-bipyridyl)iron(II) following the reaction of metaformin with Fe^{3+} -bipyridyl. The reaction proceeds through the reduction of Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} with the subsequent formation of an intense orange-red colouration attributed to the complex (2–20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The absorption spectra of the coloured complex under optimum conditions were scanned in double beam made against a reagent blank over the range 400–900 nm, and recorded

according to general procedure. Characteristic λ_{max} value was obtained at 550 nm.

Effect of reagent concentration :

The addition of 1.0 ml of Fe^{3+} -bipyridyl solutions is sufficient to obtain the maximum and reproducible absorbance for 6.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of metaformin. Smaller amounts resulted in complete complex formation. Increased concentration had no effect on complex formation, although absorbance increased slightly owing to the reagent background used.

Effect of temperature and heating time :

The effect of temperature and heating time on the formation of the colored complex were also studied. The reaction of metaformin with the reagent proceeded very slowly at room temperature with higher temperature employed to accelerate the reaction. Maximum absorbance was obtained following on a water bath at 100 °C for about 15 min with Fe^{2+} -bipyridyl colored complex. Further heating caused no appreciable change in the color. The complex obtained was highly stable for more than 12 h.

Effect of acid strength :

The reaction product orange red was found to flocculate within 20–30 min of colour development. The orthophosphoric acid was added to the drug solution to give stable colour and results are compared to HCl.

Detection and quantification limits :

According to the analytical methods committee the detection limit LOD is the concentration of metaformin corresponding to a signal equal to the blank mean plus three times the standard deviation of the blank (S_B). Quantification limit (LOQ) is the concentration of metaformin to the blank mean plus ten times the standard deviation of the blank. The LOD and LOQ values for metaformin with 2,2-bipyridyl were found to be 0.13 and 1.85 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Accuracy precision and recovery studies :

The validity of the methods for the assay of metaformin was examined by determining precision and accuracy. These were analyzing six replicates of the drug within the Beer's law limits. The low values of relative standard deviation (RSD) indicate good precision of the method.

The results of analysis of dosage forms are given in Table 2. The results are reproducible as evident from low RSD values.

Assay in formulation :

Twenty tablets of metformin was weighed to obtain the average tablet weight and then powdered. Equivalent to 10 mg of metformin was weighed and the solution was made up to 100 ml with mobile methanol. The resulting mixture was allowed to stand for 1 h with intermittent sonication to ensure complete solubility of the drug (Stock solution). This stock solution was filtered and filtrate was diluted to the desired concentration. Convenient aliquots from this solution were taken for the determination of metformin by developed method and results are shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Optical characteristics of proposed methods

Parameters	2,2'-BPL
λ_{max} (nm)	550
Beer's law limit ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	2-20
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	2.315×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001 \text{ A.U}$)	0.0015
Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.998
Regression equation (a_A) :	
Slope (<i>b</i>)	0.059
Intercept (<i>a</i>)	0.046
% Relative standard deviation ^b	1.0275
Color	Orange red
LOD ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.13
LOQ ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	1.85
<i>t</i> -test (Theoretical value - 2.306)	0.179
<i>F</i> -test (Theoretical value - 6.39)	1.40
$a_A = a + bc$, where <i>c</i> is the concentration of measured solution in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.	

^bValues in parentheses are the theoretical values for *t*- and *F*-values at 95% confidence limits and five degrees of freedom, b_A = average of six determinations.

Table 2. Determination of metformin in pharmaceutical dosage forms

Formulation	Taken ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Found ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Recovery \pm RSD
Obimet	1.0	0.999	99.94 ± 0.2074
	3.0	2.998	99.96 ± 0.0641
Fortamet	2.0	1.995	99.75 ± 0.5834
	4.0	3.997	99.94 ± 0.0326

Table 3. Method accuracy from recovery assay for the studied analyte

Sample	Added ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Found ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Recovery \pm SD
Urine samples (10%)			
1	2.0	1.989	99.46 ± 0.339
2	4.0	3.996	99.91 ± 0.115
3	6.0	5.997	99.95 ± 0.031

Analysis of recovery of metformin from urine samples :

The urine samples were obtained from healthy volunteers. The urine samples were prepared for the recovery of metformin with this proposed method. The urine samples were centrifuged for 15 min at 3000 r/min to remove the suspended matter before determination. The urine samples were added respectively according to the proposed procedure. The results are presented in Table 3. High accuracy and good recoveries are obtained, which indicates that the proposed method can be successfully applied to recover metformin in the urine samples.

Conclusions

The reagents used in the developed method are cheaper, readily available and the developed method does not involve any critical reaction conditions or tedious sample preparation. The method is unaffected by slight variations in the experimental conditions, such as pH, reagent concentration or temperature. The developed method is sufficiently sensitive to permit determinations even down to 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The sensitivity in terms of molar absorptivity and precision in terms of RSD of the method are very suitable for the determination of metformin in tablets and human urine samples. Moreover, the methods are free from interference by common additives and excipients.

The method also represented very high accuracy and precision. So that the respective standard deviation and relative error of prediction for drugs were lower than 1%. These advantages encourage the application of the developed method in routine quality control analysis of metformin in pharmaceutical and human urine sample.

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